

Efficient discovery of Novel Endogenous Pararetrovirus in plant genomes.

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Abstract. Endogenous Pararetroviral (ePRV) sequences encapsulate thousand years of viral-host interactions within plant genomes, acting as markers of evolutionary history. To exploit the potential of these ePRVs requires precise identification and annotation, as the scientific community strives to understand their broader implications of their presence on host plants. To systematically uncover ePRVs across plant genomes, we employed a Hidden Markov Model profile-based scan and BLAST algorithm for search and annotate respectively, that according to our experiments provided the best search performance. This rigorous computational approach enabled the accurate pinpointing of ePRV coordinates in multiple genomes. High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources facilitated extensive searches across 51 genomes, enabling efficient handling and analysis of large-scale data. The information generated forms the backbone of an in-house database that allows to explore further relationships between ePRVs and other genome components. This database, aside from housing raw sequence data and sequence annotations, provides extensive metadata, including genomic location, contextual genetic information and insights into potential ePRV-induced gene modulation. We also have identified complete viral genomes and truncated ePRV sequences, suggesting possible roles these viral remnants play in traits as fruit development, resilience to environmental stressors, and even disease resistance. This study enhances our understanding of ePRVs and their function, laying the groundwork for future biotechnological applications in crop improvement and disease resistance.

Keywords: ePRV, endogenous pararetrovirus, plant genome annotation.

1 Introduction.

1.1 Unveiling Endogenous Pararetroviruses in Plant Genomes

The presence of endogenous pararetrovirus (ePRV), a genome-integrated double-stranded DNA pararetrovirus from the *Caulimoviridae* family, has been reported in several plant genomes such as rice (*Oryza sativa*) [1], tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) [2], banana (*Musa paradisiaca*) [3], Maqui (*Aristotelia chilensis*) [4], Petunia (*Petunia hybrida*) [5], among others. Recent studies indicate that these might not only represent molecular fossils, but could play a role in pathogenicity, contribute to resistance [6] or be related to the development of plants, demonstrating that ePRVs are not always neutral sequences [7]. Pararetroviruses present a retrotranscription cycle, similar to other retroviruses, but they do not need to integrate into the host genome for replication since they can do so as episomes [8]. Nonetheless, pararetroviruses display conserved genomic structures, such as a movement protein (MP), a capsid or coat protein (CP) harboring a CCHC-type zinc finger, and a POL-like polyprotein comprising a protease (PR), a reverse transcriptase (RT) and a RNase-H (RH) [9].

Recent reports showed several approaches used to discover ePRVs, mainly focused on analyses of molecular biology, genomic and transcriptomic data of cultivated crops [10-13]. Notably, the complete relationship between the presence of ePRVs in plant genomes and plant development is not yet completely understood, and their annotation is a confusing task due to the lack of an established approach for identification and classification methods for endogenous virus in plant genomes. Nevertheless, in the same way as the *Caulimoviridae* family, some ePRVs can replicate and initiate viral infection, under different environmental stresses and are known to cause a variety of different phenotypes, such as chlorotic tissues, leaf malformation, vein-clearing symptoms and other affections [4]. Some authors have suggested that ePRVs may also play a role in resistance to viral infection [2, 5, 14].

Based on the evidence up to date, we could suggest that a relationship between ePRVs and key processes in plants exists, so the development of a reliable method for the detection of complete ePRV sequences and partial ePRVs is of great relevance. In this way, proper annotation is deemed to help in the development of biotechnological applications on commercial crops, such as the early detection of endogenous viruses or ripening markers, which could help to the diagnosis of plant susceptibility to viruses.

2 Methodology

2.1 Search of ePRV sequences and databases.

The first step of this work consists on the creation of a database that serves as the basis for the identification, annotation and classification of ePRV sequences in plant genomes. The collection of PRV and ePRV sequences was searched for the keywords: pararetrovirus, ePRV, endogenous pararetrovirus, in the next public databases: NCBI

[15], ENA [16], DDBJ [17] and the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses [18]. We retrieved, from these public repositories all available PRV and ePRVs, collected PRV sequences include current viruses representing each genus of the *Caulimoviridae* family: *Cauliflower mosaic virus* (NC 001497.2), *Tobacco vein clearing virus* (NC 003378.1), *Carnation etched ring virus* (NC 003498.1), *Cacao swollen shoot virus* (NC001574.1), *Blueberry red ringspot virus* (NC 003138.2), *Cassava vein mosaic virus* (NC 001648.1), *Cestrum yellow leaf curling virus* (NC004324.3), *Petunia vein clearing virus* (NC 001839.2), *Soybean chlorotic mottle virus* (NC 001739.2), *Sweet potato col-lusive virus* (NC 015328.1), *Sweet potato vein clearing virus* (MH188860.1), *Rose yellow vein virus* (NC 020999.1), *Banana streak virus* (NC 008018.1), *Cassava vein mosaic virus* (NC 001648.1), *Commelina yellow mottle virus* (NC 001343.1), *Horseradish latent virus* (NC 018858.1) and *Rice tungro bacilliform virus* (NC001914.1). Importantly, very few ePRV sequences have been annotated and recorded from plant genomes, and most of them were only recorded as supplementary material in published works [2-4, 12].

The ePRVs sequences collected in the first database search were classified into complete viral genome sequences and open reading frame sequences (ORFs), using as reference both the genome and ORFs of the *Cauliflower mosaic virus* (CaMV), which is a member of the genus *Caulimovirus*, one of the six virus genera and the most representative virus sequences of the *Caulimoviridae* family [4, 12]. Our classification, based on the presence/absence of ORFs allowed to define and separate the complete viral sequences of PRV, ePRV and ORFs: MP, PR, RT and RH sequences downloaded from databases and research articles, we registered 194 endogenous viral sequences belonging to PRV, ePRV and *Florendovirus* [12]. We next created a database with standard sqlite (<https://www.sqlite.org/index.html>) to serve as storage and catalog for all other ePRV sequences for future research. This database contains complete sequences of the ePRV genome, ORFs and plain text with the information on biological and genetic characteristics, that will be updated for each genome that will be processed. All PRV and ePRV sequence information collected from the biological databases is available in Supplementary File 1.

2.2 Search tool performance analysis

We next compared several commonly used methods and tools to search for biological sequences in databases, such as methods based on similarities: BLAST+ based on all against all local alignments [19], global alignments based on the implementation of Needleman Wunsch algorithm used by Needle [20] and profile of the hidden Markov model used by HMMER [21]. To test and compare the performance of the algorithms, the search aims to identify as top hits the ePRV sequences in the database as positive examples. As negative examples, required to assess type I and II errors, we used the association of ePRV with members of the plant retrotransposon family (*Ty3-gypsy/copia* elements) frequently reported in ePRV research as examples of false members of the ePRVs yet with sequences highly similar to actual ePRVs [5, 22]. These retrotransposon sequences were obtained through a keyword and sequence similarity search in the NCBI nt database. The result was filtered with an identity equal or greater than 50%

and a query coverage equal or greater than 50% [23, 24], resulting in 249546 matches and their coordinates were used to extract the FASTA sequences from NCBI nt database using Bedtools getfasta [25]. The extracted sequences were grouped at 90% with the CDHIT tool [26] and the small sequences less than and equal to 500bp were filtered out, obtaining 948 sequences of retrotransposons as true negatives [24]. For this test, finally we used 194 registered endogenous viral sequences belonging to PRV, ePRV and *Florendovirus* as positive examples and 948 sequences belonging to plant retrotransposons. The selection of the alignment, coverage and identity parameters for all the tools were based on different studies of the estimated range where the sequence similarity decreases between pairs of aligned sequences and the ability to detect true positives tends to decrease and increase the number of false positives [27]. At a certain level of sequence similarity, the number of false positives exceeds the number of a true positives. The zone in which this occurs has been labeled the “twilight zone” [23, 28-31]. This range of sequence similarity is used to infer homology by similarity is based on pairwise alignment identity of at least 40%, a threshold often used to evaluate all homology search tools [23]. The protocol followed to test the tools employed in this study was a leave-one-out (LOO) validation approach [32]. A total of 1,142 sequences were used in the execution of the LOO validation process, which included 194 viral sequences and 948 retrotransposons. Each method was used to search for ePRV sequences with all other ePRV sequences serving as the query, applying default search parameters.

For BLASTN, each query sequence was classified using the other sequences as the database [19, 24]. The following command was used to create the classifier sequences: `makeblastdb -in allsequences.fasta -input_type fasta -dbtype nucl -out classifier.DB`. The BLASTN command employed was `BLASTN -query allsequences.fasta -db classifier.DB -outfmt '6 qseqid sseqid pident qlen length mismatch gapopen qstart qend sstart send eval evalue bitscore' -num_alignments 1141 -out one_vs_all.txt`. The results were formatted in output 6 for easier manipulation. The identity provided by each BLASTN search alignment was used to fill the confusion matrix, allowing for the calculation of observed and predicted classifications.

For Needle, all 1,142 sequences were aligned using the command options `-asequence` and `-bsequence` using all the sequences for each entry, with the default settings `-gapopen 10 -gapextend 0.5`. The identity of each alignment was used to populate the confusion matrix [20].

The protocol for nHMMER differed slightly, as it employed a ten-fold cross-validation approach due to the higher computational cost of training Hidden Markov Models (HMMs). Both viral and retrotransposon sequences were divided into 10 equally sized sets. For each set, an HMM profile was created using the remaining nine sets, aligned using CLUSTALO with default parameters [33]. HMM profiles were generated using the command `hmmbuild --dna profile1.hmm evirus_align.aln`. Each HMM was then used to search all other sequences within the database. This process was repeated across all sets, allowing the completion of the confusion matrix and the generation of the list of observed and predicted classifications [23, 34].

To determine their performance, we used a confusion matrix in which the recovered ePRV examples that are classified as ePRVs are true positives or false negatives if they are classified as non-ePRV, or retrotransposon sequences are false positives if they are more similar to ePRVs or true negatives when they are correctly classified. After completing the LOO, metrics such as precision (P) and sensitivity (S) were calculated to compare the different search methods and determine which is the best of all [35].

$$\text{Precision } P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}; \quad \text{Sensitivity } S = \frac{TP}{TP+FN};$$

where TP are true positives (ePRV sequences classified as such); FP are false positives (retrotransposon sequences classified as ePRVs) and FN are false negatives (ePRVs classified as retrotransposons). All outputs and the management of the resulting tables were handled through custom Python scripts and RStudio, with the source code made available on GitHub at https://github.com/networkbiolab/ePRV_search

2.3 ePRVs search and occurrence report

Using nHMMER as our search method, we employed it to identify ePRV sequences across various genomes. The output table from nHMMER was processed to generate a BED file containing the genomic coordinates of ePRV sequences, which was subsequently used to extract the corresponding FASTA sequences from the respective genomes. Additionally, a GFF file was created, detailing the genomic coordinates of each pro-viral ePRV sequence identified. This method was applied to Tomato SL4 genome (<https://solgenomics.net/>) as well as several fruit tree genomes: *Vitis vinifera* NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>), *Malus domestica* Phytozome release v13 (www.phytozome.net), *Prunus persica* genome v2 (<https://www.rosaceae.org/organism/24333>), *Fragaria vesca* genome v1 (http://www.rosaceae.org/projects/strawberry_genome), *Jatropha curcas* Genome DataBase (<http://www.kazusa.or.jp/jatropha/>), and *Arabidopsis thaliana* database (<https://www.arabidopsis.org/>). Additionally, we evaluated all genomes previously described by Geering et al. [12]. The genomic locations of ePRV sequences, along with their corresponding GFF files, FASTA sequences of complete viral ePRV genomes, and associated ORFs, were systematically stored in the previously described database. This methodology was consistently applied across all studied genomes. High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources were utilized to parallelize the analysis, enabling the efficient handling of the large-scale genomic datasets.

3 Results

3.1 The first collection of PRV and ePRV.

The search of sequences in biological databases (NCBI, ENA, DDBJ), using keywords related to “pararetrovirus”, “endogenous pararetrovirus” and sequences of the *Caulimoviridae* family, allowed to establish the first steps for the creation of a specific viral database. The collection of viral genome sequences allowed to find 98 PRVs, 20 ePRVs from biological databases and 76 endogenous viral genome sequences categorized as part of the genus *Caulimovirus*, called "*Florendoviruses*" not stored in any database but described in the complementary information published by *Geering et al.*, [12]. The complete information of the 117 complete genome sequences obtained from NCBI was stored and classified into complete genome sequences, ePRV, ORFs and regulatory sequences.

The search for ePRV sequences was performed using Blastn, Needle and nHMMER tools [19, 20, 23, 34], the extraction of specificity and sensitivity of each tool was tested through a cross-validation LOO method, with the purpose of finding the tool that allows to better identify ePRVs in plant genomes. For this, we used 194 registered endogenous viral sequences belonging to PRV, ePRV and *Florendovirus* as positive examples and 948 sequences belonging to plant retrotransposons frequently reported in ePRV research with an evolutionary relationship [5, 22]. The selection of false examples or negative sequences was based on the close relationship of retroviruses, retrotransposons and PRV, which includes a similar sequence and a reverse transcriptase. Plant retrotransposons, PRVs and ePRVs, contain a primer binding site (PBS), with a tRNA^{met} primer and a RT used in the replication step [36], these similarities make retrotransposons a good negative example for validation of the search method.

The tools used for the search of ePRV sequences showed similar values of precision and sensitivity in discriminating between viral endogenous sequences and retrotransposons. The search methods with the highest recognition of true positive sequences are observed in the Blastn and nHMMER tools, which also present values close to 1 in sensitivity (Table 1) [23]. NEEDLE classified 189 sequences as ePRV or true positive, 942 retrotransposons as true negative, 6 false positive (retrotransposon sequences classified as ePRV), and 5 false negative (ePRV classified as retrotransposon). The Blastn default values were used for the LOOV search, for each sequence or test set, it was evaluated by all the remaining sequences or training sets and it was evaluated as a positive prediction if the PID obtained is equal to or greater than 50% coverage and all hits less than this value were classified as negative [34], obtaining as ePRV 190 true positive, 947 retrotransposons as true negative, 1 false positive and 4 false negative. NHM-Mer classified 194 true positive ePRVs, 940 of retrotransposons as true negative, 8 false positive and 0 false negatives.

Table 1.- Confusion matrix for Blast, HMMer and Needle tools in the recognition of ePRV sequences. The table shown True Positives (TP) indicate correctly identified ePRVs, True Negatives (TN) indicate correctly identified non-ePRVs (retrotransposons), False Positives (FP) are

retrotransposons misidentified as ePRVs, and False Negatives (FN) are ePRVs misclassified as retrotransposons. Precision and Sensitivity were calculated using the standard formula.

	TP	TN	FP	FN	Precision	Sensitivity
Blastn	190	947	1	4	0.995	0.979
NHMMer	194	940	8	0	0.96	1
Needle	189	942	6	5	0.969	0.974

3.2 Annotation of plant genomes.

Based on the results observed in the confusion matrix, HMMs and Blastn alignments were used as methods for the recognition of viral endogenous sequences in the genome of 51 different plants (Table 2) [12].

Table 2.- Occurrence of endogenous viral sequences to the genomes of various plant species. Columns represent the species name, total genome size (MB), number of identified ePRVs, total size of ePRV sequences (MB), and the percentage of the genome composed of ePRVs. The data highlights the varying extent of ePRV integration within different plant genomes.

Species	Genome size MB	ePRV	Size MB ePRV	% of plant genome comprising ePRV
<i>A. chilensis</i>	354.1	381	0.6	0.17
<i>A. thaliana</i>	119.1	245	0.16	0.13
<i>C. sinensis</i>	299.8	4905	6.68	2.23
<i>S. lycopersicum</i>	782.5	16012	10.95	1.40
<i>V. vinifera</i>	485.3	3809	4.06	0.84
<i>A. coerulea</i>	302	949	1.2	0.40
<i>A. trichopoda</i>	706.3	9197	14.9	2.11
<i>B. distachyon</i>	271.2	804	0.64	0.24
<i>C. clementina</i>	301.4	4464	5.77	1.91
<i>C. papaya</i>	370	6241	2.96	0.80
<i>C. sativus</i>	224.8	1058	1.07	0.48
<i>E. grandis</i>	615.9	2967	3.08	0.50
<i>E. guttata</i>	321.6	1130	1.35	0.42
<i>F. vesca</i>	214.2	802	0.89	0.42
<i>G. raimondii</i>	750.2	9795	6.87	0.92
<i>J. curcas</i>	266.8	1585	2.25	0.84
<i>L. usitatissimum</i>	306.4	561	0.24	0.08
<i>M. esculenta</i>	639.6	21835	16.06	2.51
<i>M. domestica</i>	703	3841	3.61	0.51
<i>O. sativa</i>	373.8	1837	1.34	0.36
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	521.1	2434	1.84	0.35
<i>P. persica</i>	227.4	964	1.29	0.57
<i>P. virgatum</i>	1100	11727	8.2	0.75

<i>M. acuminata</i>	472.2	2114	1.88	0.40
<i>Z. mays</i>	2200	28003	17.49	0.80
<i>G. max</i>	978.4	6432	6.51	0.67
<i>T. aestivum</i>	14600	136315	122.61	0.84
<i>C. arabica</i>	1100	12574	13.91	1.26
<i>T. cacao</i>	324.7	2128	1.41	0.43
<i>D. carota</i>	421.1	1514	1.38	0.33
<i>C. lanatus</i>	361.3	2396	1.81	0.50
<i>S. tuberosum</i>	705.8	10856	7.77	1.10
<i>B. oleracea</i>	488.6	1614	1.16	0.24
<i>C. annuum</i>	3200	92811	66.74	2.09
<i>C. sinensis</i>	3100	34375	28.46	0.92
<i>O. europaea</i>	1100	11290	10.31	0.94
<i>S. indicum</i>	274.9	1434	1.61	0.59
<i>N. tabacum</i>	3600	82778	44.71	1.24
<i>S. splendens</i>	805.9	6388	5.54	0.69
<i>C. reticulata</i>	344.3	6338	6.27	1.82
<i>P. granatum</i>	320.3	1825	1.96	0.61
<i>C. illinoensis</i>	674.3	7198	7.96	1.18
<i>H. annuus</i>	3000	87629	65.59	2.19
<i>B. rapa</i>	352.8	2441	1.83	0.52
<i>V. radiata</i>	463.1	1721	1.32	0.29
<i>P. inflata</i>	1290	16520	13.7	1.06
<i>F. ananassa</i>	805.7	3909	4.21	0.52
<i>B. vulgaris</i>	568.8	4450	3.72	0.65
<i>C. sativa</i>	875.7	5395	3.17	0.36
<i>R. communis</i>	315.6	4976	8.04	2.55
<i>C. rubella</i>	133.1	320	0.26	0.2

PRVs and ePRVs were stored in a local SQL database with the objective of integrating all the information of plant viral endogenous sequences. To do so, information was distributed in tables with the following information stored in each table: location of PRV and ePRV in each genome (coordinates and ORFs), sequences of each ePRV and its ORFs and verification when available (e.g, previously known ePRVs in the genome of *S. lycopersicum*). Thus, this database avoids the major limitations of other biological databases, such as sequence redundancy and lack of curation, typically ending up in a super-set of information or miss-annotated records. In contrast, specialized databases provide curated records that have detailed information, with the genomic information of the complete sequences, in addition to the information of the ORFs and regulatory sequences present in each complete pararetrovirus genome, CP, MP, PR, RT and RH sequences.

The presence of complete viral genomes, including key functional domains such as reverse transcriptase, RNAse-H, and movement protein, suggests that these sequences may play active roles in the regulation of gene expression, particularly during critical developmental stages including fruit ripening [24]. The potential for these ePRVs to influence relevant traits such as stress response, disease resistance, and developmental processes, especially in a commercially important crops, makes the study of ePRVs highly relevant. Thus, accurate annotation of ePRVs is the mandatory first step without which the study of ePRVs is not possible. Understanding the interaction between these

viral sequences and the host genome could provide new insights into plant-virus co-evolution and pave the way for innovative approaches to crop improvement [37, 38]. By integrating ePRV data into a specialized, non-redundant database, this research offers a valuable resource for further studies, facilitating the exploration of ePRV functions and their implications for tomato breeding and genetic research.

4 Discussion

The comprehensive identification of endogenous pararetrovirus (ePRV) sequences in all evaluated plant genomes underscores the significance of these viral elements in plant development and gene regulation. The use of HMMs facilitated the identification of hundreds of thousands of ePRV sequences within plant genomes, reflecting the complexity and evolutionary significance of these elements. For example, in tomato (*S. lycopersicum*) 773 of these sequences exhibited high similarity to previously identified ePRVs, suggesting that ePRVs are not merely genomic remnants but may play active roles in regulating gene expression, particularly during the fruit ripening process [36]. The presence of complete viral genomes and functional domains such as reverse transcriptase, RNase-H, and movement protein further supports the hypothesis that ePRVs may influence critical traits such as stress response and disease resistance [24, 38]. Given the genome sizes in plants, much larger than for other groups of eukaryotes and the relatively high cost of any of the three tested search approaches, the application of HPC significantly improved the computational throughput, allowing for the simultaneous processing of multiple genomes and ensuring the rapid and accurate identification of ePRV sequences across diverse species. [39]. The resulting database provides a curated resource that facilitates further exploration of ePRV functions, particularly their potential to modulate gene expression. These findings lay the groundwork for future research into the role of ePRVs in plant-virus co-evolution and their potential applications in crop improvement [40].

5 Conclusion

The identification and annotation of ePRV sequences highlights the significant presence and potential functional roles of these elements in plant genomes. This study successfully identified thousands of ePRV sequences, providing insights into their possible contributions to gene regulation and plant development. The creation of a specialized database for ePRVs ensures that this information is accessible and can be used to inform future research and biotechnological applications, particularly in understanding the genetic factors influencing tomato ripening and disease resistance. Further investigation into the functional implications of ePRVs, particularly their role as precursors of small RNAs and their interaction with host gene expression, will be crucial in uncovering their full potential and impact on plant biology.

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